

Cosmological Inflation of Compressed Lorentz Manifold - 8 Theory

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Abstract:

In this paper, analysis of the new 8-Theory, a varying curvature framework which manifested in a varying Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g_E)$ with signature (3,1), which is the connected Einstein manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. Such a manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter. The arbitrary variation term has been discretized and partitioned $\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$ to create threefold combination of two distinct elements varying. The main equation will be analyzed in the context of cosmological inflation and singularity. The manifold was always in existence. The difference is a shift from a compact to an uncompact manifold, due to a moment in which $\delta g \neq 0$ yielding an outward acceleration

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\delta g = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$\mathbf{0}: \delta g_1 \rightarrow \delta g_2 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 = 0 \quad (1.18)$$

To:

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 + \delta g_2 \neq 0 \quad (1.181)$$

We proved that in order to bring the element back to where it was and to attach it to itself it takes an additional map on the varying element, to a threefold combination. The threefold combinations are creating cyclic group, the elements of the cyclic group are themselves cycles.

$$\mathbf{Y}: \delta g_2 \rightarrow \delta g_1 \quad (1.182)$$

$$\delta g_1(0) \delta g_2(Y) \delta g_1 \quad (1.183)$$

Notice that the manifold has no beginning. It was always exit. We can define the cosmological inflation as the shift from a compressed Lorentz manifold, or compact, to an uncompact manifold. Such a shift is due to a curvature not vanishing at a certain moment

$$\delta g \neq 0$$

Invoking immediately a dual response by the second term required stationary manifold:

$$\delta g' \neq 0$$

Since the manifold was compact at the time, it could mean highly dense, so the term could resemble a Dirac delta. Such a sharp hyperbole than would be immediately flatten by wrapping universes, yielding an acceleration outward of the manifold. The uncompact manifold than resemble a high-energy thermal stage aspiring a colder state due to the expansion. It is the same expansion and acceleration we investigate those days according to the 8T. We have represented the main equation in the additional way:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.184)$$

The uncompact manifold, due to its size than experience noticeable arbitrary variations, which vanish into matter. Any prime amount or one than causing ripples across the manifold, i.e. bosonic propagations. As time goes by, weaker and weaker interactions will manifested by the coupling constant equation and the principle of least variation.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.01)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2.011)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$\frac{N_V}{T_V} \rightarrow 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{9} = 0.111 : \frac{3}{30} = 0.1 : \frac{5}{128} = 0.039 \dots$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots$$

The bosonic propagations gets more and more flat, weaker and less noticeable. That suits very well the weakness of gravity, and the immense gap among, the third element, i.e. the electric, and the unknown in order gravity.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)